

Mobile Technologies applied to protect victims of a crime within the EU Area of Justice: RightsApp for e-Justice

D5.7 Public events

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1	Description of past and future public events regarding RightsApp project	31/08/2020	Jorge Gonzalez-Conejero (IDT-UAB)
2	Proofreading	08/09/2020	Pompeu Casanovas (IDT-UAB)

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document collects all the information regarding the public events related to the RightsApp project. The information includes name, location, organizer, responsible within the RightsApp project, number of attendants, materials, presentations, among others.

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1 EVENTS

The dissemination of the main outcomes to the public is a key task that is carried out during the whole project lifespan and even after the finalization of the funded period. Therefore, the RightsApp research team has been continuously looking for opportunities within the 30 months of the project. Initially, two public events were planned in M19 and M24, respectively, however, the opportunities to disseminate the outcomes to the public that appeared and the onset and spread of the COVID-19 forced the RightsApp team to reshape the initial plans. The main changes are:

- From the very beginning, different opportunities to disseminate the objectives and the main outcomes of the project took place. These events were also key from a networking point of view, and most of the institutions that are actively collaborating with the project now were contacted for the first time in these events. Therefore, the first public event that was initially planned for the month M19 of the project has been replaced with:
 - Participation in the “Online support to crime victims” event (see Section 1.1)
 - Participation in the “2nd Research Workshop for Lecturers and Professors of Criminology” event (see Section 1.2)
 - Participation in the “New challenges, new answers: innovation and urban security” (see Section 1.3)
 - Participation in the “Research Workshop of the Scottish Centre for Crime & Justice Research” (see Section 1.4)

To sum up, Table 1 lists the events, month of the project and the number of attendants of every face-to-face event aimed at disseminating the RightsApp objectives and/or main outcomes.

Event	Held month	Number of attendants
Online support to crime victims	M0	75
2 nd Research Workshop for lecturers and Professors of Criminology	M4	20
New challenges, new answers: innovation and urban security	M13	55 ¹
Research Workshop of the Scottish Centre for Crime & Justice Research	M21	40
Total		190

Table 1: Summary of the months and number of attendants of face-to-face events

Regarding the public event that was initially planned to be held in M24, during the project lifespan, two amendments that affected the duration of the project were submitted and accepted. Thus, the last month of the project changed to M30 instead of M24 and as a consequence, the last main public event was moved to the last month of the project. Unfortunately, the onset and spread of the COVID-19 that started on month M24 and M25 of the project had a significant impact on research and dissemination activities.

¹ This number was informally reported by the organization as the number of attendants to the poster session.

One of the main drawbacks for the RightsApp project was that face-to-face meetings were strongly discouraged, and the most part of the workshops, conferences and public events had been postponed or cancelled. Against this background, the RightsApp team have prepared a set of materials to perform an “Online Infoday” event (see Section 1.5). In addition to these materials, activities and events, the RightsApp research team is preparing a face-to-face public presentation for September 2020 (see Section 2), however, if the COVID-19 situation prevents the celebration of the presentation it will be moved to an online activity.

1.1 Online support to crime victims

The first event to report was held before the starting date of the project. The RightsApp research team benefited from the possibility of introducing the motivation, needs, objectives and expected main outcomes to an audience of lawyers, psychologists, doctors, social workers, among others.

Table 2 briefs the details of the event and the link to the information published about the event in the RightsApp Home Page. The RightsApp presentation and the whole session were recorded and uploaded to: <https://youtu.be/weazj1RaUaY?t=4713>. Figure 1 depicts two screenshots from the video when the RightsApp project was introduced to the audience.

Event	Online support to crime victims
Title	RightsApp project
Organizer	Catalan Society of Victimology (<i>Societat Catalana de Victimologia, SCV</i>)
Information published at the RightsApp Home Page	http://rightsapp-project.uab.cat/index.php/2018/01/02/on-line-support-to-crime-victims/
Date	19 th December, 2017
Project month	M0 (the project started the 1 st March 2018)
Place	Universitat Oberta de Catalunya facilities in Castelldefels, Barcelona, Spain.
Responsible	Dr. Jorge Gonzalez-Conejero
Audience	Stakeholders and practitioners (lawyers, psychologists, doctors, social workers, among others)
Number of attendants	75 people
Language of the event	Spanish
Language of the materials	Spanish

Table 2: Online support to crime victims event details

In this event, no achievements nor outcomes were presented since the project started after the event was held; however, Spanish Red Cross and the Catalan Society of Victimology were contacted, and they became active collaborators of the RightsApp project²³.

Figure 1: Screenshots from the video of the session when RightsApp project was presented

1.2 2nd Research Workshop for Lecturers and Professors of Criminology

The second reported event was hosted by the Criminology and Criminal Law Department at the UAB. Dr. Maria José Rodríguez Puerta was invited to introduce the RightsApp project within the “Victims and the use of ICT in crime prevention” time slot of the workshop. The event was named as “2nd Research Workshop for Lecturers and Professors of Criminology” and its main audience was mainly composed by lecturers and Professors on Criminology and Criminal Law matters. The RightsApp team considered the attendance to this event as a worthy opportunity since the project was running M4 and the main effort was focused on finding out and analysing key sources for the project⁴, most of them legal sources. Therefore, the presentation consisted of motivations, needs, expected achievements as well as the ongoing work of identification of key sources.

Table 3 briefs the details of the event and the link to the information published on the RightsApp Home Page regarding this event. Figure 2 depicts the agenda of the event and Figure 3 shows the English version of the presentation used to introduce the RightsApp project. Although the event took place mainly in Spanish, the presentation was translated and uploaded to the RightsApp Home Page for dissemination purposes.

Event	2nd Research Workshop for Lecturers and Professors of Criminology
Title	Victims and the use of ICT in crime prevention
Organizer	Criminology and Criminal Law Department of the UAB
Information published on the RightsApp Home Page	http://rightsapp-project.uab.cat/index.php/2018/06/25/771/

² See RightsApp D5.4 Mid-project International Workshop. Available online at: <https://zenodo.org/record/3545857>

³ See RightsApp D5.9 Final International Workshop. Available online at: <https://zenodo.org/record/3974190>

⁴ See RightsApp Deliverable D2.1 “Report on key sources for the project”. Available online at: <https://zenodo.org/record/1282080>

Date	21 st June, 2018
Project month	M4
Place	Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Cerdanyola del Vallès, Spain
Responsible	Dr. Maria José Rodríguez Puerta
Audience	Academia
Number of attendants	20
Language of the event	Spanish
Language of the materials	The materials are available in Spanish and English ⁵

Table 3: 2nd Research Workshop for Lecturers and Professors of Criminology event details

"This event aims to boost the exchange of research experiences among the professors and lecturers of the Degree in Criminology in order to strengthen their professional ties and encourage the use of research for teaching".

2018

UAB
Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona

II Research Workshop for Lecturers and Professors of Criminology- 21 June 2018

SCHEDULE

12.30-13	Prof. Joel Martí	Social networks and criminology: research among the youth
13-13.30	Prof. Albert Pedrosa	Spanish Criminal Code and gender perspective
13.30-15	LUNCH	
15-15.30	Dra. Maria José Rodríguez	Victims and the use of ICT in crime prevention
15.30-16	Prof. Paco Collazos	Cross-cultural psychiatry programme of Vall d'Hebron Hospital
16-16.30	Prof. Roger Mancho	Neighborhoods and crime: the case of Badalona
16.30-17	COFFEE BREAK	
17-18.30	END OF COURSE PROCEEDINGS	

Organizer: Degree in Criminology
UAB – Anna Meléndez, deputy coordinator
6/21/2018

Figure 2: 2nd Research Workshop for Lecturers and Professors of Criminology schedule

⁵ Materials are available at the RightsApp home page: <http://rightsapp-project.uab.cat/index.php/rightsapp-presentation-for-the-2nd-research-workshop-for-lecturers-and-professors-of-criminology/>

RIGHTSAPP PROJECT DG-JUSTICE PROGRAMME

European Project led by the IDT and conducted by Jorge González, Emma Teodoro, Esther Zapater, Chus Guardiola and M^a José Rodríguez

This presentation has been funded by the European Union's Justice Programme (2014-2020)

RIGHTSAPP PROJECT DG-JUSTICE PROGRAMME

Goals

The RightsApp project aims to inquire on the potential of new mobile technologies for empowering the EU citizens and improving the exercise of their rights as crime victims.

The project targets the design and development of a mobile application for Android and iOS capable of furnishing crime victims with simple and understandable information about their rights and about the institutions in charge of assuring their effective exercise.

Once the App is created, a pilot test will be carried out, with students from the UAB, in order to validate the tool and evaluate its operability.

RIGHTSAPP PROJECT DG-JUSTICE PROGRAMME

Consortium:

RIGHTSAPP PROJECT DG-JUSTICE PROGRAMME

Work plan:

I. Level I

- Elaboration of an informative table containing the European, Spanish and Catalan legal frameworks concerning crime victims.
- Classification of the victims' rights granted by each legal framework and bearing in mind the special schemes stipulated in the Spanish legislation.
- Identification of the available information about crime victims at the European, Spanish and Catalan levels.
- Identification and location of the Oficinas de Atención a las Víctimas (OAVD, Spanish victim assistance offices) and other public and private assistance entities in Spain and Catalonia.
- Development of a website with information about the project.

RIGHTSAPP PROJECT DG-JUSTICE PROGRAMME

Work plan:

2. Level II

- Design of a decision tree and a survey -as well as its standardization.
- The essential elements and information levels (low, medium and high) might be identified.

3. Level III

- Creation of the application for Android and ISO (with geolocation).
- Experts validation.

4. Level IV

- Pilot test.

RIGHTSAPP PROJECT DG-JUSTICE PROGRAMME

Current accomplished goals:

- The first level has been fulfilled:
 - i. A table with the relevant legal information has been elaborated,
 - ii. The scarce data on victims compiled by the Spanish and Catalan institutions have been analysed,
 - iii. The public and private assistance entities and offices for crime victims have been identified and located,
 - iv. A website has been created.

RIGHTSAPP PROJECT DG-JUSTICE PROGRAMME

Current accomplished goals:

- The first level has been fulfilled (<https://zenodo.org/record/1282080>)
 - i. A table with the legal information –centred on the Spanish legal framework- has been elaborated.
 - ii. Among other issues, we might highlight the enactment of the ESTATUTO DE LA VICTIMA LO 4/2015 (Spanish statute of the victim) transposing the European Directive 2012/29/EU.
 - iii. Resulting from the adoption of the Estatuto de la Víctima, a new regulation on the OAVD has been enacted: Real Decreto 1109/2015, de 11 de diciembre, por el que se desarrolla la Ley 4/2015, de 27 de abril, del Estatuto de la víctima del delito y se regulan las oficinas de asistencia a las Víctimas del Delito (Spanish decree developing and implementing the Statute of the Victim).

RIGHTSAPP PROJECT DG-JUSTICE PROGRAMME

Current accomplished goals:

- The first level has been fulfilled (<https://zenodo.org/record/1282080>)
 - Together with this new regulation, further laws grant rights, though limited to the victims:
 - Ley 35/1995, de 11 de diciembre, de ayudas y asistencia a las víctimas de delitos violentos y contra la libertad sexual (Spanish law on the assistance to victims of violent and sexual crimes). Real Decreto 738/1997, de 23 de mayo, por el que se aprueba el Reglamento de ayudas a las víctimas de delitos violentos y contra la libertad sexual (Spanish decree on the aids to victims of violent and sexual crimes).
 - RD 199/2006, 17 feb., incorpora al Derecho español la Directiva 2004/80/CE que introdujo un nuevo título V "Normas para facilitar a las víctimas del delito en situaciones transfronterizas el acceso a las ayudas públicas" (Spanish decree transposing the European Directive 2004/80/EC, particularly focused on the access to public aids for victims in cross-border situations).
 - La Ley Orgánica 19/1994, de 23 de diciembre, de protección a testigos y peritos en causas criminales (Spanish Organic Law for the protection of witnesses and court experts in criminal trials).
 - PARTICULAR RELEVANCE of the special schemes, which basically target three scenarios: terrorism, gender-based violence, human trafficking, minors and people without legal capacity.

RIGHTSAPP PROJECT DG-JUSTICE PROGRAMME

Current Accomplished Goals:

- The first level has been fulfilled
 - i. The scarce data on victims compiled by Spanish and Catalan institutions have been analysed,
 - International Crime Victims Surveys (ICVS). Spain participated for the last time in 2009.
 - Public security surveys in Catalonia (ESPC, in Catalan), which provide information from 1999 onwards. Surveys on crime victim data (EVB, in Catalan), carried out by the city council of Barcelona since 1983.
 - Crime victim data related to cybercrime, which are collected since 2012, have also been analysed. This area is progressively gaining prominence.
 - ii. Information shortages have been identified, namely the lack of data on the victims' level of knowledge about their needs and rights.

RIGHTSAPP PROJECT DG-JUSTICE PROGRAMME

Proposal of activities targeting the collection of further information about crime victims in Spain, specially in Catalonia:

- Interviews with the Oficinas de Atención a la Víctima del Barcelonés (assistance offices for crime victims in the Barcelonés) aiming to know who refers the victims to their service, as well as the victims' degree of acquaintance with their rights.
- Meetings with the Conselleria de Interior de Catalunya (Catalan Department of home affairs) to propose the integration of new issues into the ESPC related to the victims' knowledge about their rights and aiming to find new strategies to improve it.
- Meetings with officers of the Barcelona city council to propose the inclusion of new issues into the EVB related to the victims' knowledge about their rights and aiming to find new strategies to improve it.

Figure 3: English version of the materials for the 2nd Research Workshop for Lecturers and Professors of Criminology

1.3 New challenges, new answers: innovation and urban security

The Security and Prevention Department of the Barcelona City Council acting as Executive Delegate of the Spanish Forum for the Prevention and Urban Security (FEPSU) organized the “New challenges, new answers: innovation and urban security” public event. As a result of the collaboration between the Security and Prevention Department and the RightsApp project, the RightsApp research members Dr. Jorge Gonzalez-Conejero and Dr. Emma Teodoro were invited to exhibit a RightsApp poster.

The event was addressed to academia, stakeholders and practitioners, and provided an excellent opportunity to disseminate the project among public. Table 4 briefs the event details and the link to the information published regarding this event in the RightsApp Home Page.

Event	New challenges, new answers: innovation and urban security
Title	Projects and experiences: RightsApp project
Organizer	Spanish Forum for the Prevention and Urban Security (Forum Español para la Prevención y la Seguridad Urbana, FEPSU)
Information published at the RightsApp Home Page	http://rightsapp-project.uab.cat/index.php/2019/03/27/rightsapp-in-new-challenges-new-answers-innovation-and-urban-security/
Date	28 th March 2019
Project month	M13
Place	Universidad Pompeu Fabra, Campus de la Ciutadella, Barcelona, Spain

Responsible	Dr. Jorge González-Conejero and Dr. Emma Teodoro
Audience	Academia, stakeholders and practitioners
Number of attendants	55 people
Language of the event	Although some of the tools and initiatives exhibited in the event were developed in English, the main language in the event was Spanish
Language of the materials	Spanish (translated into English for the deliverable)

Table 4: “New challenges, new answers: innovation and urban security” event details

Figure 4 depicts the poster of the event and Figure 5 shows Dr. Jorge Gonzalez-Conejero and Dr. Emma Teodoro with the RightsApp poster.

Figure 4: New challenges, new answers: innovation and urban security event poster

Figure 5: Dr. Jorge Gonzalez-Conejero (left) and Dr. Emma Teodoro (right) at the “New challenges, new answers: innovation and urban security” event with the RightsApp poster

Figure 6 depicts the RightsApp poster implemented by the RightsApp research team to introduce the project at the event. As mentioned above, the event was mainly conducted in Spanish, however, Table 5 lists the most relevant texts in the poster translated into English for its inclusion in this deliverable.

RightsApp project
The RightsApp project aims to improve the access to justice for European citizens via the use of mobile technologies and the effective implementation of their rights when they fall victims to a crime.
Why is RightsApp an innovative experience?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The project endows an active role to European citizens regarding the effective implementation of their rights as crime victims. • Mobile technologies are used in order to empower citizens and ensure their right to access justice. • Thanks to the details provided by the user, the mobile application furnishes the victims with suitable information considering their particular situation. • The information provided by the App is understandable by the user and minimizes the use of legal technicalities. It is available in several languages (Spanish, English, Portuguese and Italian).
Main activities and results
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The access of European citizens to justice, even in cross-border situations, has been improved. • The project has contributed to ensure a wider implementation and knowledge of the European citizens’ rights via the RightsApp application.

Table 5: English translation of the most relevant part of the RightsApp poster exhibited at “New challenges, new answers: innovation and urban security” public event

Figure 6: RightsApp poster for the “New challenges, new answers: innovation and urban security” public event

1.4 Research Workshop of the Scottish Centre for Crime & Justice Research

This public event was held in Stirling University (United Kingdom). Dr. Esther Zapater introduced the most relevant objectives, motivations and achievements of the RightsApp project to an audience mainly composed by PhD candidates, lecturers and professors of Law.

Event	Research Workshop of the Scottish Centre for Crime & Justice Research
Title	RightsApp Project: Empowering Victims
Organizer	The Scottish Centre for Crime & Justice Research
Date	27 th November 2019

Project month	M21
Place	Stirling University, Stirling, United Kingdom
Responsible	Dr. Esther Zapater
Audience	Academia (PhD candidates, lecturers and professors)
Number of attendants	40 people
Language of the event	English
Language of the materials	English

Table 6: RightsApp presentation at Stirling University

Table 6 depicts the details of the event, its language, and materials. Figure 7 shows the digital presentation poster.

Figure 7: RightsApp presentation poster in the Stirling University (United Kingdom)

Finally, Figure 8 shows the presentation of the RightsApp project slides that Dr. Esther Zapater used to introduce the RightsApp project to the audience.

Figure 8: Presentation of the RightsApp project at Stirling University (United Kingdom)

1.5 Online Infoday

Initially, this event was scheduled for M30 of the project, however, the onset and spread of COVID-19 started in month M24. This pandemic had a significant impact on research and dissemination activities since at the time of writing this report face-to-face meetings are strongly discouraged. As an example, the final RightsApp workshop that was held in M29 (23rd July 2020) booked a room to welcome the attendants, however, local authorities recommended to move the meeting to an online event (See Deliverable D5.9 “Final International Workshop”⁶). Moreover, the most part of workshop, conferences and public events that could be considered as candidates to introduce the RightsApp outcomes were postponed or cancelled. Against this background, the RightsApp team have prepared a set of materials to perform an “Online Infoday”:

- Presentation slides
 - In English in PDF format
 - In Spanish in PDF format
 - In Spanish in PPT format with explanation from the coordinator of the project
- Training videos
 - Training video in English with a tour through the Android mobile application
 - Training video in English with a tour through the iOS mobile application

Event	RightsApp Online Infoday
Title	RightsApp Infoday
Organizer	Institute of Law and Technology (IDT)
Information published at the RightsApp Home Page	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • http://rightsapp-project.uab.cat/index.php/rightsapp-infoday-presentation/

⁶ See RightsApp Deliverable D5.9 “Final International Workshop”. Available at: <https://zenodo.org/record/3974190>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • http://rightsapp-project.uab.cat/index.php/rightsapp-training-videos/
Date	From 15/04/2020 to 31/08/2020
Project month	From M26 to M30
Place	Online event
Responsible	Dr. Jorge González-Conejero
Audience	All targeted groups
Number of attendants (downloads/viewers)	54 people
Language of the event	English
Language of the materials	English

Table 7: RightsApp Online infoday details

Table 7 briefs the details of the RightsApp online infoday and the link to the information published on the RightsApp Home Page. These materials are available online. The number of attendants count as the downloads and/or viewers of these materials.

Figure 9: Infoday materials on the RightsApp Home Page

Figure 9 depicts the RightsApp Home Page information available to the general public. It shows that the online Infoday presentations are available in English and Spanish and, in addition, the Spanish version also contains a document with an audio explanation by the project coordinator. Figure 10 shows the English version of the presentation.

Right to move and reside freely within EU

- Since 1995, the Schengen Area has abolished all internal borders in lieu of a single external border, allowing EU citizens to travel without checks or visas across the 26 countries where it is in force up to date.
- Subject to certain condition, citizens of the EU have the right to move and reside freely within the territory of the EU. This right is conferred directly by Article 21 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union.
- The European strategy on the Area of Security, Freedom and Justice, was to ensure that the EU citizens' rights are protected sufficiently even when they are in a different Member State than their own.

Crime victims: issues

- Lack of awareness regarding EU and national legal framework, and consequently, lack of awareness regarding crime victim rights when citizens fall victim to crime in the EU.
- Lack of harmonization, although EU sets up common rules, legal frameworks vary from one Member State to another.
- Lack of legal background from citizens causes difficulties to understand their rights since usually these rights are listed and explained in technical and legal texts.
- Different language than your own, especially if you are abroad.

Background

- Regulation (EU) 2015/2120: Abolishment of roaming surcharges.
- Eurostat: In 2019, within the EU-27, a 77% of the European citizens surf the Internet every day.
- Eurostat: In 2019, within the EU-27, a 71% of the European citizens surf the Internet through a smartphone.
- Although at a national level English is the most widely spoken foreign language where it is not an official language, there are dramatic differences among Member States: The Netherlands (90%), Malta (89%), Denmark (86%) and Sweden (86%) are particularly likely to speak English as a foreign language, on the other hand, Italy (34%), Portugal (27%) and Spain (22%) report lower skills. (Eurobarometer 386)

The project

Main objectives

- To contribute to increase awareness, strengthening and empowering of EU citizens' rights through mobile technologies when they fall victim to a crime within the EU.
- To create a one-stop provider in EU smartphones and/or tablets regarding EU citizens' rights when they fall victim to a crime.
- To deploy a citizen-centric, user-friendly and dynamic mobile application for Android and iOS operative systems
- To provide tailored knowledge and information from different sources

The project

- Mobile Technologies applied to protect victims of a crime within the EU Area of Justice: RightsApp
- Duration: 01/03/2018—31/08/2020
- Consortium: Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona – Institute of Law and Technology, UAB Faculty of Law and International Support Service
- Funding: DG-Justice (JUST-AG-2017/JUST-JACC-EU-AG-2017)
- Home web page: <http://rightsapp-project.eu>
- Twitter: @p_rightsapp

Consortium

Collaborators

RightsApp application

Deployment of the application

Available on the App Store

Application features

- In the first quarter of 2019, Android's market share in the five largest economies in Europe (United Kingdom, France, Germany, Spain and Italy) was 79.3%, on the other hand, the iOS's market share was the 20.1%.
- It models the Spanish legal framework.
- It is deployed in: Spanish, English, Italian and Portuguese.
- It considers three different scenarios:
 - To make an emergency call to 112.
 - To provide tailored information regarding crime victim rights (through a short questionnaire).
 - To provide information regarding crime victim support centres and entities, and consulates and embassies.

Main screen

How to use the app / Change language

Emergency call to 112

Emergency call to 112

Crime victim rights

Questionnaire design (1)

Questionnaire design (2)

- Features from the Spanish legal framework (See deliverable D2.1: <https://zenodo.org/record/1282080>)
 - Directive 2012/29/EU establishing minimum standards on the rights, support and protection of victims of crime.
 - Act 4/2015, April 27th, Statute of the Crime Victims in Spain.
- The questionnaire allows to obtain information regarding crime victim rights for the user or for a third person.
- Terrorism, Violence against women, Domestic violence, Violent crimes and against sexual freedom. (Deliverable D2.3: <https://zenodo.org/record/1745372>)
- Victimization survey from Barcelona (2012-2019).

Questionnaire design (3)

- Terrorism
 - This crime is one of the crimes listed in the questionnaire
- Violence against women
 - Violence perpetrated by the partner/ex-partner when the victim is a woman
- Domestic violence
 - Violence perpetrated within the family unit when the victim is not a woman and/or the perpetrator is not the partner/ex-partner
- Violent crime
 - The assault entails physical and/or psychological consequences to the victim
- Crime against sexual freedom
 - Sexual assault to the victim

Questionnaire design (4)

Crime victim rights (Android)

Crime victim rights (iOS)

Crime victim support centres and entities

Search of centres and entities (1)

- The application uses three criteria for the search of crime victim support centres and entities:
 - Entity type (Crime victim support offices, Police stations, etc.)
 - Country where the centres/entities are located. In this version of the application only Catalonia (Spain) is available.
 - City where the centres and/or entities are located
- The three categories are dynamic, when one of them is modified the rest are updated according to the modification. For instance, when a type of centre/entity is selected, the cities dropdown list is updated and only the cities where there are availability of the selected type of centre/entity are shown.

Search of centres and entities (2)

- In the current version of the application, the database includes: all the crime victim support offices in Catalonia; all the Mossos d'Esquadra (Catalan Police) police stations where citizens could report a crime, and the consulates and embassies located in Barcelona.
- Once the criteria is selected, the application returns a list with centres/entities that matches the selected criteria. This list is sorted by proximity to the user: from the closest to the furthest. (This option will require permissions to access the user location)
- Once the user selects one centre/entity from the list, the application shows more detailed information about the centre/entity in a new screen. From this new screen the user is able to call, write and e-mail, surf the centre/entity home page or navigate to it through the default navigation application in the user's smartphone.

Search of centres and entities (Android)

Search of centres and entities (iOS)

Survey

- The main idea of this survey is the evaluation in terms of usability of the mobile application RightsApp by the user.
- If you are going to take this survey without being the victim of a crime, please imagine a situation where you have been the victim of one or more crimes so that you can test all aspects of the RightsApp application.
- The entire UAB research team that has developed the RightsApp application greatly thank you for your participation. Your voluntary participation and contribution are key for achieving the objectives of this technological solution.
- <https://forms.office.com/Pages/ResponsePage.aspx?id=KUNRaSEfMUJ3dITXEWAX4qoBFP51Nv0HXGRfArZUQUrNIVBNOEVMmJA1QUVRMFMVWVNNNUdRfU>

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IDT Institute of Law and Technology

UAB Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona

UAB Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona Facultat de Dret

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Figure 10: Infodays main presentation in English

Figure 11: RightsApp training videos in the RightsApp Home Page

Figure 11 depicts the RightsApp training videos that are available on the RightsApp project home page.

2 FUTURE EVENTS

The Institute of Law and Technology (IDT) as coordinating institution of the project has the commitment to continue developing and promoting the RightsApp project and its main outcomes even after the funded period. Therefore, the two scheduled next steps regarding public events are:

- **UAB Alumni network.** The RightsApp research team is working on a face-to-face public presentation with the UAB Alumni Network in order to disseminate the main outcomes of the RightsApp project. The presentation is scheduled for September 2020, however, if COVID-19 prevents the celebration of this presentation it will be moved to an online activity.
- **Public event for stakeholders and academia.** As soon as the COVID19 situation remits a face-to-face public event will be held to report and show the project developments and main achievements to stakeholders and academia. We are preparing this event jointly with Institut d'Estudis Catalans (IEC)⁷. The IEC is a centre for Catalan studies and, with its sections and subsidiary companies, promotes and develops research in the different fields of science and technology. It works as a centre for disseminating research and also hosts, at its headquarters, research initiatives from other institutions that are closely related.

From a general perspective, the next step scheduled by the RightsApp research team is to introduce the mobile applications to the tourism sector in Barcelona, Catalonia and Spain. The main objective is to locate QR codes with the mobile applications and its corresponding explanation in the major hotels and touristic centres. However, the COVID-19 situation has delayed this plan since the tourism industry is now on standby.

⁷ Institut d'Estudis Catalans (IEC). Home page available at: <http://iec.cat>